

An iron(III)-Schiff base complex as a functional model of phenoxazinone synthase enzyme

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Abstract : A new iron(III) complex, [Fe(L)Cl₂(H₂O)] (**1**) containing a (N,O,Cl)-donor Schiff base ligand has been synthesized and characterized by different analytical techniques. Room temperature magnetic measurement indicates the existence of high spin iron(III) compound in the solid state. Molar conductance value of the iron compound in methanol medium reveals the existence of 1 : 2 type electrolyte in solution. The structural formulation of the iron-Schiff base complex has been confirmed through optimization with B3LYP density functional theory (DFT) using 6-31g(d) basis set and shows that the proposed structure is in better agreement with the experimental findings. The iron(III) complex has been evaluated to mimic the active site of phenoxazinone synthase enzyme in methanol medium. The iron(III) complex significantly promotes the catalytic oxidation of 2-aminophenol (AP) to 2-aminophenoxazin-3-one in under aerobic condition with a high turnover number, $k_{\text{cat}} = 4.32 \times 10^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$.

Keywords : Iron(III), Schiff base, phenoxazinone synthase activity.

Introduction

In this modern era, new and efficient metal catalyst towards oxidation reactions in industry and synthetic processes for different kinds of organic transformations create paramount interest to elucidate the basic functional principles that govern such metallic reactivity of natural enzymes¹⁻⁴. Binding and activation of small molecules such as dioxygen takes place at the active site of different natural enzymes in biology, which also helps to model the reactivity of the metalloenzymes in regard to finding new catalysts for selective oxidation reactions under mild conditions. Iron is a bio-essential element and in the evolutionary process this metal has become an integral part of many metabolic processes including safe disposal pathways⁵⁻⁷. Iron complexes feature not only a broad spectrum of oxidation states but also the ability to transfer one or two electrons to a substrate which opens up the possibility either for radical reactions, or for two-electron transfer processes which commonly proceed in metal-catalyzed coupling reactions⁸.

The enzyme phenoxazinone synthase is involved in the last stages of the biosynthesis of Actinomycin D a naturally occurring antineoplastic agent⁹. Herein, we have synthesized and characterized a new iron(III) complex containing a (N,O,Cl)-donor Schiff base ligand. Also, we report the investigation of bio-mimicking activity of the iron-Schiff base complex towards phenoxazinone synthase activity. The iron complex significantly promotes the catalytic oxidation of 2-aminophenol (2-AP) to 2-aminophenoxazin-3-one in methanol medium under aerobic condition with turnover number, $k_{\text{cat}} = 4.32 \times 10^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and solution properties of the iron(III) complex :

The complex **1** was prepared by mixing of ferric chloride and the Schiff base ligand in 1 : 1 molar ratio in methanol solvent. The complex has been isolated as a brown coloured crystalline compound. Based on elemental analysis and other fundamental spectroscopic

techniques the complex **1** was formulated as $[\text{Fe}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$. Room temperature magnetic measurement indicates the +3 oxidation state of the iron centre as reveal from $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 5.9$ BM. The complex was soluble in common organic solvents such as MeOH, MeCN and DMSO.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of the Schiff base ligand and its iron(III) complex.

The UV-Vis spectrum for iron(III)-Schiff base complex in methanol medium shows high intensity transitions in the range of 200 to 300 nm and a broad transition in the range 350 nm to 550 nm. The bands at 261 and 299 nm are assigned to π - π^* transition of the C=N chromophore corresponding to Schiff base ligand, whereas the bands originated at 387 and 521 nm is due to ligand to metal charge transition, suggesting the coordination of imine nitrogen and phenolate oxygen with Fe^{III} ion¹⁰.

In order to investigate the solution stability of the complex in methanol medium we perform variable concentration conductivity measurements at room temperature under aerobic condition. For this, we have taken three different solution of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ and $1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ concentration and plotted a graph \sqrt{C} vs molar conductance (Fig. S1). The nature of plot indicates 1 : 2 electrolytic behaviour of the complex in solution. The iron(III) complex in methanolic solution releases two chloride ions from the primary zone of coordination and acts as $[\text{Fe}(\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+} : 2\text{Cl}^-$ electrolyte. Further, the pH of the solution of the iron(III)-Schiff base complex in MeOH became 4.7 and suggested that release of coordinated chloride ions in the form of HCl molecules in solution. This behaviour is further consolidated by ESI-MS spectrum which shows the base peak at m/z 335.34 for $[[\text{Fe}(\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+} + \text{H}^+]$ species.

Molecular modelling analysis :

Though we have isolated the compound in polycrystalline phase but failed to produce single crystals

instead of repeated attempts in different solvent mixture and conditions, we tried to assess the observed data at molecular level with the help of molecular modelling in DFT technique. Molecular modelling had been successfully used to detect three dimensional arrangements of atoms in complex by means of semi-empirical molecular orbital calculations at the B3LYP level using 6-31g(d,p) basis set provided by the Gaussian 09 suite. Their utilization in the demonstration of molecular structure and structural properties data of the iron(III) complex conducted with calculated HOMO and LUMO energies, selected bond lengths and bond angles of the iron complex is presented in Table 1. The optimized structure of the penta coordinated iron(III) complex is shown in Fig. 1. In the gas phase, the tetradentate (O,N,Cl)-donor Schiff base ligand (L) exhibits its bidentate behaviour towards Fe^{III}

Table 1. Theoretically calculated bond distances (Å) and angles (°) for Fe^{III} -Schiff base complex

Bond type	Distances (Å)	Bond type	Distances (Å)
Fe1-N1	2.035	Fe1-O2	1.824
Fe1-O1	1.957	Fe1-C12	2.261
Fe1-C11	2.258		
Bond angles			
Bond angle type	Angle (°)	Bond angle type	Angle (°)
N1-Fe1-O1	90.1	C11-Fe1-C12	91.9
N1-Fe1-C11	90.4	O2-Fe1-C12	90.3
N1-Fe1-O2	87.6	Fe1-N1-C13	120.7
N1-Fe1-C12	177.6	O1-Fe1-C11	92.3
Fe1-N1-C8	123.2	O1-Fe1-O2	99.8
C11-Fe1-O2	167.8	O1-Fe1-C12	89.1

Fig. 1. Computational optimized structure of the iron(III)-Schiff base complex (**1**).

centre and forms a square pyramidal iron(III) complex in its optimized structure. Besides the ligational motifs of Schiff base ligand, the coordinative saturation of iron(III) centre is completed by two chloride ions from ferric chloride salt and one aqua molecule from the solvent system. Non-involvement of chlorine atom and methoxy groups in the Schiff base ligand may be due to the steric crowding and electronic repulsion from the primary zone of coordination around iron(III) centre. The structure of iron(III) complex seems to be a distorted square pyramid in gas phase. The important geometric parameters of the iron(III) complex are presented in Table 1 and details geometric parameters of the iron(III) complex are presented in Table S1. The iron(III)-ligand bond lengths vary from 1.824 to 2.261 Å and the maximum bond length in iron(III) complex is found as 2.261 Å for Fe1-C12. The maximum bond angle is found in iron(III) complex as N1-Fe1-C12 = 177.6° and the minimum bond angle is O1-Fe1-C12 = 89.1°.

The difference between HOMO and LUMO is a measure of the reactivity of the compound. According to the electronic behavior, HOMO acts as electron donor and LUMO acts as electron acceptor. The calculated energy gap between HOMO and LUMO in Fe^{III} complex is -46.917 kcal/mol (Fig. 2). Here, smaller energy gap between HOMO and LUMO of the iron(III)-Schiff base complex recommends its more reactive nature^{11,12}. HOMO-1 as localized molecular orbital is a π bond between C13-C14 with 50.42% p orbital on C13 and 49.58% p orbital on C14. HOMO is mainly the lone pair on O27 with 100% p character. LUMO is a vacant p orbital on C2 adjacent to O27-C7 π bond. LUMO+1 orbital is the vacant π^* orbital on C12-C13.

Catalytic oxidation of 2-aminophenol :

The phenoxazinone synthase activity of the iron(III) complex was studied using 2-aminophenol (2-AP) as a convenient model substrate, in air saturated methanol

Fig. 2. Frontier molecular orbital's contribution in the ground state of iron(III)-Schiff base [HOMO-1 as localized molecular orbital is a π bond between C13-C14 with 50.42% p orbital on C13 and 49.58% p orbital on C14. HOMO is mainly the lone pair on O27 with 100% p character. LUMO is a vacant p orbital on C2 adjacent to O27-C7 π bond. LUMO+1 orbital is the vacant π^* orbital on C12-C13].

solvent at room temperature (25 °C). For this purpose, a $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution of the iron(III)-Schiff base complex was treated with $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ (100 equiv.) of 2-AP and the course of the reaction was followed by recording the UV-Vis spectra of the mixture at an interval of 15 min for 3 h.

Spectral bands at 261, 299, 387 and 521 nm appeared in the electronic spectrum of the iron complex in methanol, whereas 2-AP showed a single band at 267 nm. As the reaction proceeded, there was a gradual decrease in intensity of the band at 267 nm¹³ and an initial new broad band with increasing intensity was formed in the region 400–430 nm (Fig. 3), which indicated the formation of the respective phenoxazinone species^{14–16}. The phenoxazinone was purified by column chromatography and isolated in high yield (81.6% for **1**) by slow evaporation of the eluant. The product was identified by ¹H NMR spectroscopy. ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 500 MHz) δ_H : 7.62 (1H, m), 7.48 (3H, m), 6.41 (1H, s), 6.30 (1H, s).

Kinetic studies were performed to understand the extent of the efficiency. The kinetics of oxidation of 2-AP were determined by the method of initial rates and involved monitoring the growth of the phenoxazinone band at 412 nm as a function of time¹⁴ (Fig. 4). The experiments were performed at a constant tem-

Fig. 3. Increase of phenoxazinone band at 412 nm after addition of 10 equivalents of 2-AP to a solution containing iron complex (**1**) in MeOH at 25 °C. The spectra were recorded after every 15 min. Inset : Time vs Absorbance plot.

perature of 25 °C under aerobic conditions. The rate constants versus concentration of the substrate plot were also analyzed on the basis of the Michaelis-Menten approach of enzymatic kinetics to get the values of the parameters $v_{\max} = 1.20 \times 10^{-3}$ (Sd. error. 4.88×10^{-4}), $K_m = 2.06 \times 10^{-2}$ (Sd. error 2.11×10^{-3}) and $k_{\text{cat}} = 4.32 \times 10^3$. The observed rate constant versus substrate concentration plot for iron(III) complex in MeOH is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Increase of quinone band at 404 nm after addition of 100 equivalents of (3,5-DTBC) to a solution containing complex (**1**) ($10^{-4} M$) in methanol at 25 °C. The spectra were recorded after every 5 min.

The high catalytic efficiency value ($k_{\text{cat}}/K_M = 2.09 \times 10^5$) for **1** also indicates its high reactivity towards aminophenol oxidation. We also investigate the effect of catalyst concentration on reaction rate and the rate of catalytic oxidation increase with increasing the concentration of iron(III)-Schiff base catalyst in a linear manner (Fig. 5). Reuse of this iron(III)-Schiff base catalyst for aminophenol oxidation was also examined under similar reaction conditions after completion of catalytic oxidation. The reused iron(III) catalyst exhibited no change in reactivity after three cycles also.

On the basis of the literature survey of the phenoxazinone chromophore, it is suggested that a mechanism in which 2-aminophenoxazinone formation proceeded via a quinone imine intermediate that was trapped by a second molecule of 2-aminophenol. Oxi-

Fig. 5. Effect of catalyst concentration with rate of aminophenol oxidation by iron(III) complex.

dation of that adduct to the p-quinone imine was followed by a second conjugate addition and a final 2-electron oxidation to give the product, 2-aminophenoxazinone¹⁷. In order to evaluate the mechanistic aspects of the catalytic cycle by iron(III) complex (Scheme 2) for the oxidative coupling products phenoxazinone, mass spectral analysis plays a fundamental role. Mass spectral analysis of the reaction mixture in methanol medium under atmospheric condition provides valuable information regarding the reactive species and product formed in the reaction. The mass spectrum of the reaction mixture (Fig. 6) exhibits mainly the characteristics peaks at m/z 214.09 and 416.18 with isotope distribution patterns which further consolidated the corroboration respectively [(2-

Scheme 2. Proposed mechanistic pathways for aminophenol oxidation by iron(III) complex.

amino-3*H*-phenoxazine-3-ones) + H⁺] and [[Fe(2-aminophenol)(L)(H₂O)] + H⁺]. Further, the characteristic peak at m/z ~ 416 nm indicates the presence of coordinated iminobenzosemiquinonato radical during the generating apx product. Fiedler and co-workers recently isolated and structurally characterized an iron(II)-2-aminophenolate complex, [(TpPh₂)-Fe^{II}(BuAPH)], which was converted to an iron(II)-2-iminobenzosemiquinonato radical species upon one-electron chemical oxidation¹⁷.

Conclusion

A new iron(III) complex with a (N,O,Cl)-donor Schiff base ligand has been synthesized and isolated in good yield. Structural, spectroscopic and solution properties of the compound have also been investigated. The iron complex has been evaluated to mimics the active sites of phenoxazinone synthase enzyme and significantly promotes the catalytic oxidation of 2-aminophenol (2-AP) to 2-aminophenoxazin-3-one in methanol medium under aerobic condition with turnover number, $k_{cat} = 4.32 \times 10^2 \text{ h}^{-1}$. The catalytic oxidation maintains first order saturation kinetics with high catalytic efficiency.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

High purity *o*-vanillin (Sigma-Aldrich, USA), *o*-chloroaniline (E. Merck, India) and ferric chloride (E. Merck, India) and all other solvents were purchased from the respective concerns and used as received. 2-Aminophenol (2-AP) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Corporation (St. Louis, MO, USA). All the chemicals and solvents were of analytical grade and were used as received without further purification.

Physical measurements :

Elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. IR spectra (KBr discs, 4000–300 cm⁻¹) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer FT-IR model RX1 spectrometer. Ground-state absorption measurements were made with a Jasco model V-730 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The ¹H nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectra were recorded on a Bruker DPX-500 MHz spectrometer. Electrospray ionization

Fig. 6. ESI-MS spectrum of the reaction mixture of iron(III)-Schiff base complex with 2-aminophenol in methanol medium.

(ESI) mass spectrum was recorded using a Q-tof-micro quadrupole mass spectrometer. Molar conductivity was recorded using a Metler conductivity meter. A Gouy balance was used to determine the magnetic moments of the powdered samples, employing Hg^{II} tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) as a calibrant. Diamagnetic corrections were made from the Pascal's constants.

Preparation of HL and iron(III) complex 1 :

The Schiff base ligand, HL was synthesized following a previously reported method¹⁸. To prepare the Schiff base ligand, *o*-vanillin (0.1522 g, 1 mmol) was stirred with *o*-chloroaniline (0.1270 g, 1 mmol) in 50 ml dehydrated alcohol on a magnetic stirrer for 4 h and yellowish-red coloured crystalline compound was separated out from solution, which was dried and stored

in vacuo over CaCl_2 for subsequent use. Yield : 1.8450 g (70.5% based on metal salt). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{NO}_2\text{Cl}$ (1) : C, 64.25; H, 4.62; N, 5.35. Found : C, 64.29; H, 4.58; N, 5.39%; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 500 MHz) δ_{H} : 13.56 (1H, s, -ArOH), 8.75 (1H, s, -HC=N-), 7.47 (1H, d), 7.33 (2H, m), 6.99 (2H, t), 6.87 (1H, t), 3.89 (3H, s, -OCH₃); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3371 (ν_{OH}), 1616, 1601 ($\nu_{\text{C=N}}$); UV-Vis (λ_{max} , nm, MeOH, 10^{-4} M) : 254, 282, 357.

A methanolic solution of HL (0.2617 g, 1 mmol) was added dropwise to a methanolic solution of FeCl_3 (0.163 g, 1 mmol) in the same solvent (20 ml). The red solution of the ligand turned into brown and after filter the supernatant liquid was kept in air for slow evaporation. Yield : 0.101 g (64% based on metal

salt). Anal. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{13}NCl_3O_3Fe$ (**1**) : C, 41.47; H, 3.23; N, 3.45. Found : C, 41.55; H, 3.19; N, 3.51%; ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$, 500 MHz) δ_C : 167.6 (-CH=N), 155.2 (Ar-OCH₃), 151.8 (Ar-OH), 144.9 (Ar-N=C), 131.6, 128.2, 124.1, 119.3, 115.5 (Ar-C), 52.8 (-OCH₃); ESI-MS ($[1+H]^+$, MeOH) m/z 406.68; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3417 (ν_{OH}), 1628, 1605 ($\nu_{C=N}$); UV-Vis (λ_{max} , nm, MeOH, 10^{-4} M) : 261, 299, 387, 521.

Computational details :

All the electronic structures calculations were carried out using the Gaussian 09 programme suite¹⁰. Without symmetrical constrains, all geometries for ground states (S_0) were optimized with gradient-corrected exchange functional B3LYP and [6-31g(d)] basis set¹⁹. All minimized geometries were checked by frequency calculations to be true minima. A widely used gradient corrected correlated functional is the LYP functional of Lee, Yang and Parr. A popular gradient-corrected exchange functional is one proposed by Becke in 1988. The combination of the two forms the B-LYP method. The best known of these hybrids functional is Becke's three-parameter formulation; B3LYP model is used as it is a hybrid model with corrections for both gradient and exchange correlations.

Catalytic oxidation of 2-aminophenol :

In order to examine the phenoxazinone synthase activity, 1×10^{-3} M solution of **1** in MeOH was treated with 10 equiv. of 2-aminophenol (2-AP) under aerobic conditions at room temperature. Absorbance vs wavelength (wavelength scans) of the solution was recorded at a regular time interval of 15 min for aminophenol oxidation in the wavelength range 300–800 nm. Kinetic experiments were performed spectrophotometrically with complex **1** and 2-AP in MeOH at 25 °C for aminophenol oxidation activity. 0.04 mL of the complex solution, with a constant concentration of 1×10^{-3} M, was added to 2 mL of 2-AP of a particular concentration (varying its concentration from 1×10^{-3} M to 1×10^{-2} M) to achieve the ultimate concentration of the complex as 1×10^{-3} M. The conversion of 2-aminophenol to 2-aminophenoxazine-3-one was monitored with time at a wavelength of 412 nm (time scan)

in MeOH. To determine the dependence of rate on substrate concentration, kinetic analyses were performed in triplicate.

Effect of catalyst concentration on the reaction rate for the catalytic aminophenol oxidation in MeOH medium was determined by varying the concentration of iron(III)-Schiff base complex (5×10^{-3} M to 5×10^{-4} M) with a constant 1×10^{-2} M concentration of each substrate. Here, the kinetic analyses were performed also in triplicate.

Detection of presence of hydrogen peroxide in the catalytic oxidation of 2-aminophenol :

To detect the formation of hydrogen peroxide during the catalytic reaction, the reaction mixtures were prepared as in the kinetic experiments. During the course of the oxidation reaction, the solution was acidified with H_2SO_4 to pH 2 to stop further oxidation after a certain time and an equal volume of water was added. The formed quinone was extracted three times with dichloromethane. To the aqueous layer were added 1 mL of a 10% solution of KI and three drops of a 3% solution of ammonium molybdate. The formation of I^{3-} could be monitored spectrophotometrically because of the development of the characteristic I^{3-} band ($\lambda_{max} = 353$ nm).

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